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FEATURES OF DENTAL IMPLANTATION IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS. (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

Today, dental implants are developing rapidly. Dental implants are also widely used in patients with type 2 diabetes. In this particular case of diabetes mellitus, due to high blood sugar, the patient has serious problems with the healing of primary injuries, which can lead to various side effects when dental implants are placed on the bones. There are many scientifically based indications and contraindications for implantologists about under what conditions patients can use dental implants and under what circumstances they should stop this practice.

Keywords: dental implantation, indications and contraindications, diabetes mellitus.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ К ДЕНТАЛЬНОЙ ИМПЛАНТАЦИИ У БОЛЬНЫХ САХАРНЫМ ДИАБЕТОМ 2 ТИПА. (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Сегодня зубные имплантаты стремительно развиваются. Зубные имплантаты также широко используются у пациентов с диабетом 2 типа. В данном конкретном случае сахарного диабета из-за повышенного содержания сахара в крови у пациента возникают серьезные проблемы с заживлением первичных повреждений, что может привести к различным побочным эффектам при установке дентальных имплантатов на кости. Существует множество научно обоснованных показаний и противопоказаний для имплантологов о том, при каких условиях пациенты могут использовать зубные имплантаты и при каких обстоятельствах следует прекратить эту практику.

Ключевые слова: дентальная имплантация, показания и противопоказания, сахарный диабет.

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QANDLI DIABETNING 2 TURI BILAN OG'RIGAN BEMORLARDA DENTAL IMPLANTATSIYANING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI. (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi kunda tish implantatlari odamlar organizmining boshqa sohalarida qo'llaniladigan implanlar orasida eng tez taraqqiy etyapti. Qandli diabetning 2-turi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda ham tish implantatlari keng qo'llanilmoqda. Shu aniqki qandli diabetda qondagi qand miqdorining yuqoriligi hisobiga bemor organizmida birlamchi jarohatlar bitishida muammolar yuzaga keladi va bundan tish implantlarining jag' suyaklariga birikishida ham turli nojo'ya holatlar yuzaga kelishini tahmin qilish mumkin. Bunda implantologlar uchun qanday holatdagi bemorlarga tish implantatlarini qo'llash mumkin va qanday holatlarda bu amaliyotdan voz kechish kerakligi haqida ilmiy asoslangan turli ko'rsatma va qarshi ko'rsatmalar mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: tish implantatlari, ko'rsatma va qarshi ko'rsatma, qandli diabet.

Introduction.

One of the most common endocrine diseases in the world is diabetes mellitus. This is a group of endocrine diseases associated with impaired glucose uptake and developing as a result of absolute or relative insulin deficiency, leading to hyperglycemia. According to the latest data, more than 500 million people worldwide suffer from diabetes. In the 65+ population, this prevalence is as high as 25%¹. Type 2 diabetes is characterized by muscle and liver resistance to insulin and its reduced secretion. The results of studies conducted in recent decades indicate a relationship between the level of vitamin D sufficiency and the risk of developing both diabetes itself and its chronic complications

[13]. Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a chronic metabolic syndrome characterized by hyperglycemia, glycosuria and associated metabolic disorders.[4.6] Dental implants are an effective means of replacing missing teeth. However, diabetes can be considered a relative contraindication for this type of treatment due to a slightly higher failure rate compared to non-diabetic populations. [one]. From the very first years of using dental implants in dentistry, various indications and contraindications for the use of implants in various diseases of the human body began to form, and now there are methodological recommendations that have a clear scientific basis.

Main part.

One of the important and promising areas in modern dentistry is orthopedic rehabilitation with the help of dental implants. For all its attractiveness, dental implantation has a number of absolute and relative contraindications. These include various forms of diabetes. However, to date there is no clear understanding of the issue regarding the indications and contraindications of dental implantation in patients with DM. Some experts believe that diabetes mellitus is an absolute contraindication, others believe that only decompensated diabetes mellitus is an absolute contraindication, and others simply refuse implantation, believing that this is the best way to avoid the problem.[2]. This approach is associated with the peculiarities of this disease, primarily the variety of clinical forms, undulating course, rapid change in the phases of compensation and decompensation of diabetes mellitus. However, with the advancement of modern endocrinology, as well as the technology of dental implantation, there are opportunities to revise existing provisions and reduce restrictions. Diabetes mellitus as a systemic metabolic disease is characterized by chronic hyperglycemia and changes in the metabolism of carbohydrates, fats and proteins as a result of impaired insulin secretion, insulin action, or a combination of both.[3]

One of the key points in the dental rehabilitation of diabetic patients is the restoration of the integrity of the dentition. Until recently, dental prosthetics with end defects and complete absence of teeth in such patients was carried out with removable structures. In the regulatory and methodological documentation, type 2 diabetes mellitus refers to absolute contraindications to the use of dental implants. At the same time, there are single works on the use of dental implants in this category of patients [5.7]. In type II diabetes mellitus, two main processes occur that impede the course of osseointegration during dental implantation. This is a violation of calcium absorption and activation of osteoclasts that resorb bone tissue during hyperglycemia. Thanks to the intake of drugs that regulate the level of sugar in the blood, it became possible to level these pathological changes. In patients with controlled blood sugar levels, the processes of osseointegration and healing occurred faster than in patients with unstable levels. Sixteen to seventeen implants were placed in each of the study groups. The first group, which had stable blood sugar levels of up to 10 mmol/l, had no complications. In two patients of the second group, three of the sixteen implants were rejected.[8]

When the operation is possible

- Diabetes mellitus type 2 (without hormonal regulation of diabetes);
- compensated form (glucose level is stable - at around 7-9 mol/l before surgery and during engraftment);
 - the patient is on maintenance therapy, taking hypoglycemic medications, following a carbohydrate-free diet;
 - the process of tissue regeneration in the body is not disturbed (abrasions and bruises do not lead to complications);
 - giving up bad habits (cigarettes, drinking alcohol);
 - absence of concomitant pathologies (diseases of the thyroid gland, cardiovascular and circulatory system);
 - the possibility of organizing regular monitoring by the endocrinologist and the attending physician.

What methods can be applied

Implantation in diabetics is carried out very carefully, with minimal tissue trauma in order for the healing to take place without complications. The operation can be carried out according to one of the methods:

- Instantaneous with immediate loading: The implant is placed in place of the unit just removed. The tissues are not re-injured, healing occurs naturally. A temporary prosthesis with immediate loading is installed immediately, a permanent prosthesis - as soon as the implants take root.

- One-stage (express implant): The implant is placed in place of the missing tooth when the socket is healed. A rod with a special thread is screwed into a puncture in the gum. The implants have good primary stability. A temporary prosthesis can be placed immediately.

- Classical: The prosthesis is fixed after completion of the healing phase of the implants. The rod fuses with the tissue in an unloaded state, it is covered with a gingival flap. Classical implantation for diabetics is rarely performed: a prolonged process increases the risk of complications. Osseointegration of a titanium pin with a bone in diabetes mellitus is a slow process and lasts at least six months. The probability of successful engraftment of the implant in the lower jaw is higher than in the upper.

Postoperative period: The success of the implantation performed largely depends on the actions of the patient in the postoperative period. At this time, the diabetic adheres to the following recommendations:

- takes prescribed antibiotics for 10-12 days after surgery;
- controls the level of sugar in the blood;
- conducts oral hygiene;
- visits the attending physician every 2-3 days during the month. During the rehabilitation period (until the implant takes root), visits to the dentist can be reduced to 1 time per month;
- gives up bad habits. [9]

At the present stage, it is known that the process of osseointegration with direct contact between the bone and the implant surface depends not only on the level of bone tissue metabolism, but also on the state of immune homeostasis of the oral mucosa of patients [9]. Therefore, the monitoring of implant integration is of absolute importance to ensure the long-term stability of dental implants in clinical practice. The results of treatment are directly dependent on the level of modern ideas about the mechanisms of pathogenesis in implant rejection and the features of reparative regeneration in periodontal structures under implantation conditions. This dictates the monitoring studies of COR in the group of dental patients with DM2 pathology to improve the effectiveness of dental implantation and guaranteed implant integration [10].

Proper selection of patients for treatment with dental implants is one of the most important factors affecting the prognosis and engraftment of implants. A major complication in dental implant integration includes traumatic surgery, in which frictional heat generated during implant placement causes necrosis of the surrounding tissues and hence lack of healing and integration. The second complication preventing bone integration is the implant recipient site with low healing potential. Some authors argue that various systemic factors such as osteoporosis, diabetes, heavy alcoholism, kidney disease, and uncontrolled metabolic disorders increase the incidence of implant rejection. However, there is insufficient data on the impact of systemic diseases, especially diabetes mellitus, on dental implant acceptance and long-term success in humans [11.12]. An increase in blood glucose levels has a direct impact on the successful achievement and long-term maintenance of osseointegration, which must be taken into account for effective treatment with dental implants. Diabetes mellitus disrupts protein synthesis at surgical sites and delays tissue healing. Also, in diabetes mellitus, the formation of an extracellular matrix around a dental implant is inhibited by accumulated glycosylation end products (AGEs) formed during irreversible molecular interactions with glucose degradation products (GDPs). Diabetes mellitus inhibits osteoblast activity and maturation, causing severe defects in bone remodeling, formation, and mineralization. In diabetes mellitus, the frequency of postoperative infection and peri-implantitis increases due to violation of the periodontal status and a decrease in the immune response, which leads to implant rejection [14.15.16].

Conclusions.

The clinical results of dental implant placement in a selected group of patients with well-controlled type 2 diabetes are encouraging. Further studies and clinical trials over a longer period are needed to determine the long-term survival of implants in various groups of diabetic patients.

When analyzing all of the above studies, certain patterns were identified that should be taken into account in the Protocol for Dental Implantation in Patients with Type II Diabetes Mellitus, presented for convenience in the format of recommendations:

1. Regular monitoring of blood glucose levels is of paramount importance. Patients with HbA1c <8% are eligible for implant therapy. Patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus should be informed about the risks of incomplete osseointegration, up to implant rejection. Before the start of dental implantation, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive examination and comprehensive treatment together with specialists from other profiles. At the initial stage, an interdisciplinary approach to the management of patients with type II diabetes mellitus, normalization of glucose, vitamin D and bone metabolism before implantation, as well as continuation of therapy and monitoring of indicators after surgery, is very important.

2. Before working with a patient, it is recommended to assess the periodontal status of patients, oral hygiene and a history of periodontitis. It is important to ensure that the clinical course of chronic generalized periodontitis is in therapeutic remission. Prophylactic periodontal therapy twice a year is necessary to maintain the health of the tissues around the implant and ensure long-term performance of the implant.

3. It is recommended to prescribe a prophylactic course of antibiotic therapy and rinsing with antiseptics as additional therapy to avoid postoperative infection.

4. Surface treatment of implants, such as hydroxyapatite and SLA (sandblasting, coarse grit, acid etching), is recommended, as they improve the osseointegration of implants.

5. If it is possible to use methods of guided tissue regeneration using bone grafts, it is recommended to avoid excessive surgical trauma, thereby facilitating the processes of reparation of the wound surface and minimizing the occurrence of postoperative infection.

6. The immediate loading protocol can be applied to patients with controlled diabetes mellitus, while conventional loading is suitable for use in patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus.

7. Appointment of complex multivitamin therapy with the use of antihypoxants in order to improve glucose and blood levels both in the preoperative period and in postoperative rehabilitation.

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